

قاموس ۲

"نسخه مخصوص پژوهشگاه اطلاعات و مدارک علمی ایران"

تحقیق، طراحی و اجرا: مهرداد نوروزی اقبالی

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جستجو

terminology

جستجو در واژه‌های مخفی

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تصویب شده نامزد

موقت نامعتبر

بسیار

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برابری در هر قسمت برابری از ابتدا برابری با کل واژه

جستجو

جستجوی مجدد

انصراف

جستجو در واژه‌های نامرئی

جستجو در

واژه

عناوین وابسته

بکار برد

بجای

پادداشت دامنه

تاریخچه

رشته موضوعی

مغفی

مغفی برای

ترجمه ۱

ترجمه ۲

ترجمه ۳

ترجمه ۴

ترجمه ۵

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فایل ورودی: انتخاب ...

گزینه‌ها:

اصطلاح اعم	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	اصطلاح وابسته	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	او:	<input type="text"/>
اصطلاح اخص	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	تاریخ ورود	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	تو:	<input type="text"/>
بکار برود	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	تاریخ بهنگام‌سازی	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	تب:	<input type="text"/>
بجای	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	مغف	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	جف:	<input type="text"/>
ترجمه ۱	<input type="checkbox"/>	مغف برای	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	جپ:	<input type="text"/>
ترجمه ۲	<input type="checkbox"/>	پادداشت دامنه	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ید:	<input type="text"/>
ترجمه ۳	<input type="checkbox"/>	تاریخچه	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	تا:	<input type="text"/>
ترجمه ۴	<input type="checkbox"/>	بسامد	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	بپس:	<input type="text"/>
ترجمه ۵	<input type="checkbox"/>	رشته موضوعی	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	رم:	<input type="text"/>

شماره آغاز یک رکورد:

خط خالی:

خطی شامل:

مشخصه واژه اصلی:

واژه:

مصرفکننده از خطوط شروع‌شده با:

شروع: انصراف:

دوسویه کردن روابط اعم و اخص:

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HTML

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HTML

[Install directory]\Web Templates\

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HTML

Home.html

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HomeReturn.html

HomeReturn.html Home.html

NoResult.html

SearchError.html

SearchResult.html

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TermView.html

RTF

[install directory]\Web Templates\images\

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HTML

HTML Tag	Description	Example	Note
<#Host>	Host Address	http://www.MyWeb.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Not used in Home.html
<#WebCGIPath>	Home.html: Main HTML file name (no ext)	Mythes	
	Others: "http://" + Host Address + Main HTML file name (no ext)	http://www.MyWeb.com/MyThes	
<#ImagePath>	Home.html: Main HTML file name (no ext) + "/Images/"	Mythes/Images/	
	Others: "http://" + HostAddress + ScriptPath + "Images/"	http:// www.MyWeb.com/MyThes/Imag es/	
<#PageDirection>	"rtl" for right to left language thesauri and "ltr" for left to right language thesauri.	ltr	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Not used in Home.html

<#Align>	"right" for right to left language thesauri and "left" for left to right language thesauri.	left	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not used in Home.html
<#R1Checked>	Internal use		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not use.
<#R2Checked>	Internal use		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not use.
<#R3Checked>	Internal use		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not use.
<#ResultRows>	The terms which are found as the result of search process.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used only in SearchResult.html Hyperlinked. Must be put in HTML table.
<#SearchString>	The searched term(s)	Asia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used only in TermView.html Not used in Home.html
<#MainTerm>	The term which is clicked by user.	Asia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used only in TermView.html Must be put in HTML table.
<#ScopeNote>	Scope Note	A geographic name.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used only in TermView.html Must be put in HTML

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			table.
<#USE>	Preferred Term		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML table.
<#UF>	Non-Preferred Terms		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML table.
<#SEE>	Preferred Term		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML table.
<#SF>	Non-Preferred Terms		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML table.
<#RT>	Related Terms	Europa	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in

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			TermView.html <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML table.
<#ABB>	Abbreviation		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML table.
<#ABF>	Abbreviation for		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML table.
<#Frequency>	Frequency	1000	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#InputDate>	Input Date	November 1972	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.

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<#ApprovalDate>	Approval Date	May 1974	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#LastUpdate>	Last Update	April 1999	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#NotValidDate>	Not Valid Date	July 2003	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#SC>	Subject category	Geo0001	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#HN>	Historical Note		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#Translate1>	First Translation		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Must be put in HTML table.
<#Translate2>	Second Translation		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#Translate3>	Third Translation		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#Translate4>	Fourth Translation		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#Translate5>	Fifth translation		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Must be put in HTML table.
<#BT>	Broader Terms	Earth	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML

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			table.
<#NT>	Narrower Terms	Iran	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Used only in TermView.html• Hyperlinked.• Must be put in HTML table.

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	Field Name	Data Type	Field Size	Required	Description	Repeatable
1	LineNumber	Number	Long Integer	Yes		No
2	TermsLevel	Number	Long Integer	Yes		No
3	Term	Text	100	Yes		No
4	RT	Memo			Related Term	Yes
5	SN	Memo			Scope Note	No
6	UF	Memo			Used For	Yes
7	USE	Memo				Yes
8	Translate1	Text	100			No
9	Translate2	Text	100			No
10	Translate3	Text	100			No
11	Translate4	Text	100			No
12	Translate5	Text	100			No
13	Frequency	Number	Long Integer			No

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14	Description	Memo				No
15	InputDate	Text	30			No
16	ApprovalDate	Text	30			No
17	LastUpdate	Text	30			No
18	Hide	Yes/No				No
19	Status	Number	Long Integer			No
20	ABB	Text	100		Abbreviation	No
21	ABF	Text	100		Abbreviation for	No
22	SC	Text	30		Subject Category	No
23	HN	Text	150		Historical Notes	No

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The screenshot shows a search dialog box with the following elements:

- Search Input:** A text box containing the letter 'ا'.
- جستجو در واژه‌های مخفی:** A checked checkbox.
- وضعیت (Status):** A section with four checked checkboxes: 'نامزد' (Engaged), 'موقت' (Temporary), 'تصویب شده' (Approved), and 'نامعتبر' (Invalid).
- پیدا (Find):** A section with two radio buttons: 'از اصطلاح جاری' (Selected) and 'از ابتدا' (From the beginning).
- اختیارات (Options):** A section with three radio buttons: 'برابری در هر قسمت' (Selected), 'برابری از ابتدا' (From the beginning), and 'برابری با کل واژه' (Full word match).
- پسامد (Suffix):** Two empty text input fields labeled 'از' (From) and 'تا' (To).
- جستجو (Search):** A button.
- جستجوی بعدی (Next):** A button.
- انصراف (Cancel):** A button.
- جستجو در (Search in):** A section with a checked checkbox for 'واژه' (Word) and several unchecked checkboxes: 'عناوین وابسته' (Related titles), 'بکار برده' (Used), 'بجای' (Instead), 'پادداشت دامنه' (Domain note), 'تاریخچه' (History), 'رشته موضوعی' (Subjective series), 'مخفف' (Abbreviation), 'مخفف برای' (Abbreviation for), 'ترجمه ۱' (Translation 1), 'ترجمه ۲' (Translation 2), 'ترجمه ۳' (Translation 3), 'ترجمه ۴' (Translation 4), and 'ترجمه ۵' (Translation 5).
- جستجو در واژه‌های نامرئج:** An unchecked checkbox.

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